

European Nucleotide Archive

Interactive Read Data Submission

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ENA Background: What is ENA?

Open platform for the management, sharing, integration and dissemination of sequence data

- **Globally comprehensive scientific record** and European node of **INSDC**
- **Broad scope** covering raw data, through layers of interpretation and context
- **Connectivity** with broader EMBL-EBI resources
- Sequence data **foundation**
- Rich submission, discovery and retrieval **software, tools and services**
- **Support** through Helpdesk and training
- **Management**, sharing, integration and dissemination of sequence data
- **Data coordination** including project-specific data hubs and portals

Archive

Platform

Submitting data to the ENA

Why is it important to share data?

- Findability
- Accessibility
- Reproducibility/Reusability
- Interoperability
- Community collaboration
- Data standards

Maximum value

Submitting data to the ENA

All data in the ENA is submitted by members of the research community

What motivates people to submit?

- Open data
- Reproducibility
- Reusability
- 3rd party access
- Archival
- **Publication**
- Downstream analyses

*The data lifecycle, from ELIXIR Europe
<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>*

Data resources at EMBL-EBI

ENA - an ELIXIR Core Data Resource

- The ENA is part of the wider ecosystem of biodata resources
- Recognised as an ELIXIR CDR and Global Core Biodata Resource by the Global Biodata Coalition
- Integration into a system of biodata resources increases value in genomics data

GLOBAL
CORE
BIODATA
RESOURCE

Data Structure at ENA

ENA Data Structure

- ENA stores huge amounts of data
 - ... from many users
 - ... with samples from many taxa
 - ... who use many different techniques
 - ... and sequence on many different platforms
- But we need to display data in a consistent manner
- A robust model is the first step in achieving this

ENA Data model

Sequence data is organised into tiers:

- **Reads:** raw sequence data
- **Assemblies:** reconstructions of actual replicons
- **Annotations:** interpretations of biological function

Annotation and **assembly** are frequently paired

ENA Metadata Model

- Data without any context has no value
- Metadata tells us how sequence data was produced
- Makes it possible to compare datasets:

“I want to see data from bacteria ...

... in the Atlantic Ocean ...

... sampled between 50-100m ...

... between April and June ...

... compared with the same from the Indian Ocean”

- Archives have spent a lot of time thinking about this!

ENA Metadata Model: Study

- Prunus genus comprises of 200 species (peach, apricot, cherry, plum) which have high level of genomic resemblance.
- Alioto et. al sequenced the genome of species of almond tree (*Prunus dulcis*).
- Compared the Texas almond genome sequence with sequenced genome of its close relative peach, and found that, in addition to other aspects, transposable elements (TEs) played a key role in their diversification.

Alioto et al, The Plant Journal (2020), doi.org/10.1111/tpj.14538

ENA Metadata Model: Study

STUDY

ENA Metadata Model: Study

EMBL-EBI Services Research Training About us EMBL-EBI

ENA Webin Submissions Portal Support Manage Account Logout

Register study (project)

Submission Details

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *

Short descriptive study title *

Study Name

Detailed study abstract *

Will you provide functional genome annotation ?

PubMed Citations Registration

Add PubMed Citations +

Study Attributes

Add Study Attributes +

ENA Metadata Model: Sample

ENA Metadata Model: Samples

The researchers took 152 samples of young leaves of Texas almond in Spain.

Multiple individuals were sampled, and the details of each sample were logged in the database.

ENA Metadata Model: Sample

STUDY

Sample

Organism: Prunus dulcis
Name: Texas1
Location: Spain

Sample

Organism: Prunus dulcis
Name: Texas2
Location: Spain

Sample

Organism: Prunus dulcis
Name: Texas5
Location: Spain

Sample

Organism: Prunus dulcis
Name: Texas6
Location: Spain

Sample

Organism: Prunus dulcis
Name: Texas8
Location: Spain

Sample

Organism: Prunus dulcis
Name: Texas9
Location: Spain

Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

Minimum amount of information expected to describe biological samples required for registration in ENA

Sample Checklists

There is a minimum amount of information required during ENA sample registration and all samples must conform to a defined checklist of expected metadata values. The most suitable checklist for sample registration depends on the type of the sample.

These sample checklists have been developed to meet the needs of different research communities. Different communities have different requirements on the minimum metadata expected to describe biological samples. For any questions regarding checklists, contact us [here](#).

Filter by accession/name/description/field name

Accession	Name	Description
ERC000035	ENA Crop Plant sample enhanced annotation checklist	The ENA Crop sample enhanced checklist has been developed in collaboration with a number of EMBL-EBI teams to capture enriched annotation of published crop plant samples that lack sufficient reported metadata and are typically associated with systematic transcriptomic realignment-based analyses.
ERC000036	ENA sewage checklist	Minimum information about sewage samples. A checklist for reporting of sewage surveillance samples associated with sequence data from metagenomic sequencing projects. This minimum metadata standard was developed by the COMPARE platform.
ERC000037	ENA Plant Sample Checklist	ENA implementation of plant specimen contextual information associated with molecular data. The checklist has been developed in collaboration with the NCBI-GenBank and iPlant data resources under the umbrella of the Genomic Standards Consortium.
ERC000038	ENA Shellfish Checklist	Shellfish contextual information associated with molecular data. The checklist has been developed in collaboration with EMBRIC Project partners.
ERC000039	ENA parasite sample checklist	Minimum information about parasite samples. A checklist for reporting metadata of parasite samples associated with molecular data. This standard was developed by the COMPARE platform and can be used for submission of sample metadata derived from protozoan parasites (e.g. Cryptosporidium) and also multicellular eukaryotic parasites (e.g. Platyhelminthes and Nematoda).

Metadata Model: Sample Checklists

- ENA metadata checklists guided by standards working groups and the communities
 - Keep up with requirements within communities
- Rich standardised metadata facilitates linking to source information
- General minimum requirements (INSDC)
 - Organism information mandatory and linked with NCBI taxonomy
 - INSDC spatiotemporal policy: mandatory provision of collection date & geographic location
 - INSDC missing value reporting

INSDC spatiotemporal metadata – minimum standards update (03-03-2023)

[Home](#) > [News & Announcements](#) > [INSDC spatiotemporal metadata – minimum standards update \(03-03-2023\)](#)

INSDC continues its aim to increase the number of sequences for which the origin of the sample can be precisely located in time and space through harmonisation of accurate geographical annotation and date and time of collection information.

Metadata Model: Plant Sample Checklist

You have selected **ENA Plant Sample Checklist**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Add custom field

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	tax_id	Text field	None	Taxonomy ID of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database . Entries in the NCBI Taxonomy database have integer taxon IDs. See our tips for sample taxonomy here
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	scientific_name	Text field	None	Scientific name of the organism as in the NCBI Taxonomy database . Scientific names typically follow the binomial nomenclature. For example, the scientific name for humans is <i>Homo sapiens</i> .
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_alias	Text field	None	Unique name of the sample. If not selected system will auto generate a unique alias
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_title	Text field	None	Title of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample_description	Text field	None	Description of the sample
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	plant developmental stage	Text field	None	developmental stage at the time of sample collection; for Plant Ontology (PO) (v 20) terms, see http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/PO , e.g. hypocotyl emergence stage (PO_0007043)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	collection date	Regular expression	None	The date the sample was collected with the intention of sequencing, either as an instance (single point in time) or interval. In case no exact time is available, the date/time can be right truncated i.e. all of these are valid ISO8601 compliant times: 2008-01-23T19:23:10+00:00; 2008-01-23T19:23:10; 2008-01-23; 2008-01; 2008.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (country and/or sea)	Permitted values	None	The geographical origin of where the sample was collected from, with the intention of sequencing, as defined by the country or sea name. Country or sea names should be chosen from the INSDC country list (http://insdc.org/country.html) .
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (latitude)	Regular expression	DD	The geographical origin of the sample as defined by latitude. The values should be reported in decimal degrees and in WGS84 system
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	geographic location (longitude)	Regular expression	DD	The geographical origin of the sample as defined by longitude. The values should be reported in decimal degrees and in WGS84 system
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	plant structure	Text field	None	name of plant structure that the sample was obtained from; for Plant Ontology (PO) terms see http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/PO , e.g. petiole epidermis (PO_0000051); if an individual flower is sampled the sex of it can be recorded here
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	plant growth medium	Text field	None	Specification of the media for growing the plants or tissue cultured samples, e.g. soil, aeroponic, hydroponic, in vitro solid culture medium, in vitro liquid culture medium. Recommended value is a specific value from EO:plant growth medium (follow this link for terms http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/EO_0007147).
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	isolation and growth condition	Text field	None	Publication reference in the form of pubmed ID (pmid), digital object identifier (doi) or url for isolation and growth condition specifications of the organism/material. Mandatory for MIGS and MIMARKS Specimen.

Metadata Model: Plant Sample Checklist

Recommended Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
✓	propagation	Text field	None	The type of reproduction from the parent stock. Values for this field is specific to different taxa. For phage or virus: lytic/lysogenic/temperate/obligately lytic. For plasmids: incompatibility group. For eukaryotes: sexual/asexual. Mandatory for MIGS of eukaryotes, plasmids and viruses.
✓	soil_taxonomic/FAO classification	Text field	None	soil classification from the FAO World Reference Database for Soil Resources
✓	soil pH	Text field	None	pH measurement of the soil; e.g. 6.2
✓	growth facility	Permitted values	None	type of facility where the sampled plant was grown
✓	sample health state	Permitted values	None	health status of the subject at the time of sample collection
✓	sample disease status	Text field	None	list of diseases with which the subject has been diagnosed at the time of sample collection; can include multiple diagnoses; the value of the field depends on subject; e.g. Charcoal rot (<i>Macrophomina phaseolina</i>), Late wilt (<i>Cephalosporium maydis</i>)
✓	ploidy	Text field	None	The ploidy level of the genome (e.g. allopolyploid, haploid, diploid, triploid, tetraploid). It has implications for the downstream study of duplicated gene and regions of the genomes (and perhaps for difficulties in assembly). For terms, please select terms listed under class ploidy (PATO:001374) of Phenotypic Quality Ontology (PATO), and for a browser of PATO (v2018-03-27) please refer to http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/PATO
✓	number of replicons	Regular expression	None	Reports the number of replicons in a nuclear genome of eukaryotes, in the genome of a bacterium or archaea or the number of segments in a segmented virus. Always applied to the haploid chromosome count of a eukaryote. Mandatory for MIGS of eukaryotes, bacteria, archaea and segmented virus.
✓	estimated size	Regular expression	None	The estimated size of the genome (in bp) prior to sequencing. Of particular importance in the sequencing of (eukaryotic) genome which could remain in draft form for a long or unspecified period. Mandatory for MIGS of eukaryotes.
✓	organism common name	Text field	None	common name of the subject organism, e.g. maize
✓	source material identifiers	Text field	None	A unique identifier assigned to a material sample (as defined by http://rs.dwg.org/dwc/terms/materialSampleID), and as opposed to a particular digital record of a material sample) used for extracting nucleic acids, and subsequent sequencing. The identifier can refer either to the original material collected or to any derived sub-samples. The INSDC qualifiers /specimen_voucher, /bio_material, or /culture_collection may or may not share the same value as the source_mat_id field. For instance, the /specimen_voucher qualifier and source_mat_id may both contain 'UAM:Herps:14', referring to both the specimen voucher and sampled tissue with the same identifier. However, the /culture_collection qualifier may refer to a value from an initial culture (e.g. ATCC:11775) while source_mat_id would refer to an identifier from some derived culture from which the nucleic acids were extracted (e.g. xatc123 or ark/2154/R2).
✓	subspecific genetic lineage rank	Text field	None	further information about the genetic distinctness of this lineage by recording additional information i.e. variety, cultivar, ecotype, inbred line; it can also contain alternative taxonomic information
✓	subspecific genetic lineage name	Text field	None	name of the infraspecific rank, e.g ecotype Col-0
✓	...	Text field	None	...

Metadata Model: Plant Sample Checklist

Add custom field

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Recommended Fields

Optional Fields

Selection	Field Name	Validation	Units	Description
<input type="checkbox"/>	observed biotic relationship	Permitted values	None	Description of relationship(s) between the subject organism and other organism(s) it is associated with. E.g., parasite on species X; mutualist with species Y. The target organism is the subject of the relationship, and the other organism(s) is the object.
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample collection method	Text field	None	The method employed for collecting the sample. Can be provided in the form of a PMID, DOI, url or text.
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample storage temperature	Regular expression	°C	temperature at which sample was stored, e.g. -80
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample storage location	Text field	None	Location at which sample was stored, usually name of a specific freezer/room. Indicate the location name.
<input type="checkbox"/>	soil_taxonomic/local classification	Text field	None	soil classification based on local soil classification system
<input type="checkbox"/>	soil_taxonomic/local classification method	Text field	None	reference or method used in determining the local soil classification
<input type="checkbox"/>	soil type	Permitted values	None	Description of the soil type or classification. This field accepts terms under soil (http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO_00001998). Multiple terms can be separated by pipes.
<input type="checkbox"/>	soil type method	Text field	None	reference or method used in determining soil series name or other lower-level classification
<input type="checkbox"/>	soil texture measurement	Text field	% sand/silt/clay	the relative proportion of different grain sizes of mineral particles in a soil, as described using a standard system; express as % sand (50 um to 2 mm), silt (2 um to 50 um), and clay (<2 um) with textural name (e.g., silty clay loam) optional.
<input type="checkbox"/>	soil texture method	Text field	None	reference or method used in determining soil texture
<input type="checkbox"/>	sampled age	Text field	None	age of subject at the time of sample collection; relevant scale depends on species and study; e.g. 2 weeks old
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample wet mass	Text field	None	measurement of wet mass at the time of sample collection; e.g. 0.23 g
<input type="checkbox"/>	sample disease stage	Text field	None	stage of the disease at the time of sample collection, e.g. inoculation, penetration, infection, growth and reproduction, dissemination of pathogen

ENA Metadata Model: Experiments

ENA Metadata Model: Experiments

mRNA was extracted from each of the samples.

cDNA was made from this, and sequenced on an Illumina HiSeq 2000.

ENA Metadata Model: Experiments

ENA Metadata Model: Runs

ENA Metadata Model: Runs

The result of these 6 paired end experiments is 12 FASTQ files.

These are compressed and uploaded to a database, where they undergo processing and wait to be made public.

```
@SRR2960126.1 1/1
GCCAGCTATATCAGTTTCCTTTGTGATGGGGCGTTTATGTAAGGGATGGGTATGGAACGCACCCCTGGCTAGAACGAAAAGACTTGCTAT
TGTGAAGTTA
+
=;?AD=D?FDB???ACGHGGEHCEEHC@GDG>GDGHFF@9?C<38BFEACHIID>EEC>A3@D;?=:ABCA?
@@A8=B=B>89>ACCCACCADC3@4@@A
@SRR2960126.2 2/1
GTGGGTAACATTTGGAACAGAAAAACAAAAGTAGAATGGTGGGTGAGGAGAACAATAAAAAATGATACTTCATTTAATTATCATTTAGA
GATGTATATC
+
CCCFDFDFHHHHHIIJIIJJJJJJJJJJII?
DGIJJJJBFIFFGGIJJIIJJJJHHHHHFFFFFFFDEEEEDFEDEEEDEEEEDDDDDDEEFFDD
@SRR2960126.3 3/1
CTTTTAAACAAAGATTTTTTAAAAAATGCTGTGCTGTAATCTACTAGCAAAAACTAATTTGCTAGTTGCATTGGAAGATATTGATACT
TGACAATTTA
+
CCFFFFFHDDFFGHHHJIIJJIIJJJJIIJIGHIIJJJJIIJJJJJJJJIGJIHGHHHHFFFFFFFEDCCADCDDDEEEDDD
DDDDDDDDDD
@SRR2960126.4 4/1
GCTTTTTTTCGGCAACGATGGAATCGATCAATTGTTATTGTGACAGCTAAATTGATAAAACAAAATGATACAGTTTCAAACCTGATCAAAA
ATTTGCAGCA
+
@=?DDDBDFBHD<FBHAHBD@FGIEDHGH?7BB9BFGHIDF@====FCGEGGGH3AEHC;@@DDF@C>;A@AC:
5-5;>@C@CCC::@ACBA@C:4>:(2
```

ENA Metadata Model: Runs

Metadata Model: Read Submission Checklist

You have selected **Fastq File Type**. Please select the checklist fields below.

Show Description

Search fields

Mandatory Fields

Selection	Field Name	Field Label	Permitted Value	Description
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sample	Sample		Sample alias or accession.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	study	Study		Study alias or accession.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	instrument_model	Instrument model	Permitted values	The sequencing instrument model used in the experiment
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_name	Library name		The name for the library if any.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_source	Library source	Permitted values	The type of source material that is being sequenced.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_selection	Library selection	Permitted values	The method used to select for or against, enrich, or screen the material being sequenced.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_strategy	Library strategy	Permitted values	The sequencing technique intended for this library.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	library_layout	Library layout	Permitted values	The library layout specifies whether to expect single or paired configuration of reads.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	forward_file_name	Forward file name		Please enter compressed fastq the file name including any subdirectory name
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	forward_file_md5	Forward File checksum		The file MD5 checksum. This field is mandatory if you do not use the Webin File Uploader or upload the checksum using a .md5 file.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	reverse_file_name	Reverse file name		Please enter compressed fastq the file name including any subdirectory name
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	reverse_file_md5	Reverse file checksum		The file MD5 checksum. This field is mandatory if you do not use the Webin File Uploader or upload the checksum using a .md5 file.

ENA Metadata Model: Analysis

The Metadata Model: Analysis

```
>ENA|PEHZ01000001|PEHZ01000001.1 Insect metagenome contig_0_374_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GATACGTGTGCAGGTGCAAGGGTATGTGCATGGAGGGTGCCTGTATAGGTGCGAGGATG
TGTGGGGTGTGTAGGTGGAAGTGTGTGTGCATGGAGGATACGTGTGCAGGTGCAAGGGTA
TGTGCATGGAGGGTGCCTGTATAGTCCGAGGATGTGTGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTGAGGGT
GTGTGTAGGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTGAGTGTGTATGTGCATGGAGGGTGTGCAGGTGCAA
GGGTATGTGCATGGAGGGTGCCTGTATAGTCCGAGGATGTGTGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTG
AGGGTGTGTGTAGGGGGTGTGTAGGTGTGAGTGTGTATGTGCATGGAGGGTGTGCAGG
TGCAAGGGTATGTG
>ENA|PEHZ01000002|PEHZ01000002.1 Insect metagenome contig_2_497_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACATACTAGGGTAAAATACCCTAAAGTAGAAGCAAAAGTTA
ATATATTAACGCATAACTATGAGATACTATTTCTCTGTATGAAAATGATTAAGGATTAG
TATGAGAATCTACGGGTTTTCTATTTTCATCTGAGTTTATGTCTGAGTTCTATTATATCTA
TTTTAACGGAATAAAGAAACCTAGATACTTTTTATAACACAAGAGATATTAACAATTT
CTATTCACGTTTTATTTAGTAGGTATGAATAGAATACTATCTAAGATTCAATTAATTCAT
AATGAAAAGAAAATGAATGGTTAGAAAAAGAAAATAAAAACTTTCATTTACTTCTAGAATC
TGGTAGTAACCTAATAGAGATGATAATTTGATTTATCATGCCAAAGATTATAGCGGAGTT
AAAAATAGTGAAGTAAAAATTGACCAGTTTTGACGTGGAGTCCGCTAGATGGTCCGGGTAGGTG
GAGGTCGCTAGATGGTC
>ENA|PEHZ01000003|PEHZ01000003.1 Insect metagenome contig_4_469_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACATCATTGCTAAATGCAAGTTCTGGATGCTTTGTTGGACTT
TTCCATGAAGTGATGTTTCTCCATCATCGACAGTCAATGTTGTACGGCAATCAGGAATC
GTAGTCGATTGACTCACCGAGTCATCATCGGGCTCGAGTGTGATGAACTAATCGTG
TCTGATGCATGAAAGGTACTGGGCCAATTTGTGCGACCGAATTTGAAAAGTACGCCGTACC
TCAGGAATCATCGGTGTGGAACTTTGTAAAAACATCAGTGTCTATTTATCAAGACAGCT
TTGAAAAGGGCGCATCCGGCCACAGGGTCTTTAAGCTCAGTATTTGCCACAGTATCAGAA
AACCGGCAATACTAAACAGACCCGTGCTGCGTTTGAATAATCCTTCCAAACAGGCCCTT
CTTCGTCATTTGATCGAAATGGGGCCTGGTGGAGGTCGCTAGATGGTC
>ENA|PEHZ01000004|PEHZ01000004.1 Insect metagenome contig_8_628_CA-Am, whole genome shotgun sequence.
GACCATCTAGCGACCTCCACTCAAACCTCCAAAGGTGATTCGTAGCTTAAAAAATCCAC
TATCGCTATCGTAATGAATTTCTATCTTGAATCTCACTACCTGGTTTTTCAGCGGCTTTAA
```

Read data for one of the samples was put through an assembly program (Falcon phase) to produce a set of chromosomes that can be annotated.

ENA Metadata Model: Analysis

ENA Metadata Model: Analysis

MANIFEST FILE

STUDY	ERP54321
SAMPLE	ERS12345
ASSEMBLYNAME	ALMOND_V2
ASSEMBLY_TYPE	clone or isolate
COVERAGE	260
PROGRAM	Falcon-Phase
PLATFORM	Illumina
MOLECULETYPE	Genomic DNA
FASTA	prunus_Seq.embl.gz
CHROMOSOME_LIST	prunus_chromosome_list.txt.gz

CHROMOSOME LIST FILE

Chr01	1	Linear-Chromosome
Chr02	2	Linear-Chromosome
Chr03	3	Linear-Chromosome
Chr04	4	Linear-Chromosome
Chr05	5	Linear-Chromosome
Chr06	6	Linear-Chromosome
Chr07	7	Linear-Chromosome
Chr08	8	Linear-Chromosome
Chr0	0	multipartite

ENA Metadata Model

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Project: PRJEB32994

We sequenced the genome of the highly heterozygous almond *Prunus dulcis* cv. Texas combining short and long-read sequencing. We have assembled 227.6 Mb of the estimated 235 Mb almond genome size, of which 91% is anchored to eight pseudomolecules corresponding to its haploid chromosome complement. By phylogenomic comparison with the genomes of 16 close and distant species we estimate that almond and peach diverged around 5.88 Mya. These two genomes are highly syntenic and show a high degree of sequence conservation (20 substitutions per kb). However, they also exhibit a large number of presence-absence variants, many attributable to the movement of transposable elements (TEs). TEs have generated an important number of presence/absence variants between almond and peach, and we show that the recent history of TE movement is different between them. TEs may also be at the origin of important phenotypic differences between both species, and in particular, for the sweet kernel phenotype, a key agronomic character for almond. Here we show that in sweet almond cultivars, highly methylated TE insertions surround a gene of the biosynthesis of amygdalin, whose reduced expression has been correlated with the sweet almond phenotype. Altogether, our results suggest a key role of TEs in the recent history and diversification of almond and its close relative peach.

Show More

Secondary Study Accession: ERP115744

Study Title: Transposons played a major role in the diversification between the closely related almond (*Prunus dulcis*) and peach (*P. persica*) genomes: Results from the almond genome sequence.

Center Name: Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico/CNAG

Study Name: Almond Genome

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2019-09-09

ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2019-09-26

Read Files

Show Column Selection

Download report: JSON TSV

Get download script

Download selected files

Download All

Study Accession	Sample Accession	Experiment Accession	Run Accession	Tax Id	Scientific Name	Generated FASTQ files: FTP	
PRJEB32994	SAMEA5704668	ERX3398112	ERR3373960	3755	Prunus dulcis	<input type="checkbox"/> ERR3373960_1.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> 1.
						<input type="checkbox"/> ERR3373960_2.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> 1.
PRJEB32994	SAMEA5704668	ERX3398113	ERR3373961	3755	Prunus dulcis	<input type="checkbox"/> ERR3373961_1.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> 1.
						<input type="checkbox"/> ERR3373961_2.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> 1.

General

View: XML

XML (STUDY)

Download: XML

XML (STUDY)

Cross References: Show

Publications: Show

ORCID Data Claims: Show

Related ENA Records: Show

Data

Read Files: Hide

Sequence Files: Show

Wgs Files: Show

Tags

xref

EuropePMC

PubMed

Project description and metadata

Navigate around the object

Navigate on data

Run-centric data table

Information for a single run

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>

ENA Metadata Model: Navigation Bar

- View project metadata
- Show/hide different information about project
- Explore cross-references related to project
- Explore reads/analyses files

General

View:	XML
	XML (STUDY)
Download:	XML
	XML (STUDY)
ORCID Data Claims:	Show
Related ENA Records:	Show

Data

Read Files:	Show
Sequence Files:	Show
Wgs Files:	Show

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Secondary Study Accession: ERP115744

Study Title: Transposons played a major role in the diversification between the closely related almond (*Prunus dulcis*) and peach (*P. persica*) genomes: Results from the almond genome sequence.

Center Name: Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico;CNAG

Study Name: Almond Genome

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2019-09-09

ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2019-09-26

Related ENA Records

Result	Count
Coding	32556
Experiment	152
Assembly	1
Genome assembly contig set	1
Non-coding	12616
Sequence	8
Run	152

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Experiment: ERX3398114

Illumina HiSeq 2000 paired end sequencing

Organism: Prunus dulcis (almond)
Experiment Accession: ERX3398114
Instrument Platform: ILLUMINA
Instrument Model: Illumina HiSeq 2000
Center Name: Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico;CNAG
Library Layout: PAIRED
Library Strategy: POOLCLONE
Library Source: GENOMIC
Library Name: fps350_3
Library Selection: RANDOM

Show More

General

View: XML
Download: XML
Cross References: Show
ORCID Data Claims: Show

Data

Read Files: Hide

Tags

environment by geolocation
terrestrial

New tags feature

Read Files

Show Column Selection

Download report: JSON TSV

Get download script

Download selected files

Download All

Study Accession	Sample Accession	Experiment Accession	Run Accession	Tax Id	Scientific Name	Generated FASTQ files: FTP	
PRJEB32994	SAMEA5704668	ERX3398114	ERR3373962	3755	Prunus dulcis	<input type="checkbox"/> ERR3373962_1.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> 10
						<input type="checkbox"/> ERR3373962_2.fastq.gz	<input type="checkbox"/> 10

Annotations of ENA objects

Controlled textual annotations provided to metadata objects to facilitate search and filtering

ENA Metadata Model: Other features

Linking with external resources - the importance of Persistent Identifiers

Biosample: SAMN26894057 [↗](#)

Liver sample from a male adult *Callipepla californica*

Organism: *Callipepla californica brunnescens*

Scientific Name: *Callipepla californica brunnescens*

Sample Accession: SAMN26894057

Location: 39.08005 N 123.0891 W

Center Name: UCLA

Sample Alias: CC4441

Broker Name: NCBI

Sample Title: Liver sample from a male adult *Callipepla californica*

Collection Date: 2020-10-13

Secondary Accession: SRS13350135

Sub Species: brunnescens

Sex: male

Tissue: liver

Collected By: Carla Cicero

Sample Type: specimen

Specimen Voucher: MVZ:Bird:193975

Isolate: MVZ:Bird:193975

Geo Loc Name: USA: Cow Mountains Rec

Ecotype: not collected

Lat Lon: 39.08005 N 123.0891 W

Age: adult

Arctos Collaborative Collection Management Solution

Bird Collection - MUSEUM OF VERTEBRATE ZOOLOGY

Identifications

Attribute	Value	Determiner/Method/Date	Remark
Identification confidence	medium		
Nature of identification	geographic distribution		

Agents

File	Agent	Remark
collector	Carla Cicero	
collector	Thomas K Studley	

Identifiers and Relationships

Identifier	IssuedBy	Type	Collector Number
4441		collector number	

Occurrence

Term	Interpreted	Original	Remarks
Catalogue number	MVZ:Bird:193975	MVZ:Bird:193975	
Establishment events			Excluded
Occurrence ID	http://arctos.dat...3975?seid=5300976	http://arctos.dat...3975?seid=5300976	
Occurrence status	PRESENT		Inferred

Callipepla californica subsp. *brunnescens* (Ridgway, 1884)

Collected in United States of America

Animalia | Chordata | Aves | Galliformes | Odontophoridae | Callipepla | Callipepla californica

Subspecies: *Callipepla californica brunnescens* (Ridgway, 1884)

Location: North America | United States of America

Elevation: 884m

Basis of record: Preserved specimen

Organism ID: http://arctos.database.museum/guid/MVZ:Bird:193975 1 occurrence

Dataset: MVZ:Bird Collection (Arctos)

Publisher: Museum of Vertebrate Zoology

Reference: http://arctos.database.museum/guid/MVZ:Bird:193975

Issues: [\(Comment derived from coordinates\)](#)

PRJNA	SAMN	SRX	SRR	2893758	Callipepla californica brunnescens	4.3 GB	4.5 GB
PRJNA834144	SAMN26894057	SRX15651220	SRR19599930	2893758	Callipepla californica brunnescens	4.4 GB	4.7 GB
PRJNA834144	SAMN26894057	SRX15651219	SRR19599931	2893758	Callipepla californica brunnescens	41.0 GB	

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Secondary Study Accession:	ERP115744
Study Title:	Transposons played a major role in the diversification between the closely related almond (<i>Prunus dulcis</i>) and peach (<i>P. persica</i>) genomes: Results from the almond genome sequence.
Center Name:	Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico;CNAG
Study Name:	Almond Genome
ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC:	2019-09-09
ENA-LAST-UPDATE:	2019-09-26

Related ENA Records

Result	Count
Coding	32556
Experiment	152
Assembly	1
Genome assembly contig set	1
Non-coding	12616
Sequence	8
Run	152

ENA Metadata Model: Results

Secondary Study Accession: ERP115744

Study Title: Transposons played a major role in the diversification between the closely related almond (*Prunus dulcis*) and peach (*P. persica*) genomes: Results from the almond genome sequence.

Center Name: Centro Nacional de Análisis Genómico;CNAG

Study Name: Almond Genome

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2019-09-09

ENA-LAST-UPDATE: 2019-09-26

Related ENA Records

Assembly Links

Download data: [XML](#) [TSV](#) [JSON](#)

Accession	Description
GCA_902201215	ALMONDV2 assembly for <i>Prunus dulcis</i>

Assembly: [GCA_902201215.1](#)

We sequenced the genome of the highly heterozygous almond *Prunus dulcis* cv. Texas combining short and long-read sequencing. We have assembled 227.6 Mb of the estimated 235 Mb almond genome size, of which 91% is anchored to eight pseudomolecules corresponding to its haploid chromosome complement. By phylogenomic comparison with the genomes of 16 close and distant species we estimate that almond and peach diverged around 5.88 Mya. These two genomes are highly syntenic and show a high degree of sequence conservation (20 substitutions per kb). However, they also exhibit a large number of presence-absence variants, many attributable to the movement of transposable elements (TEs). TEs have generated an important number of presence/absence variants between almond and peach, and we show that the recent history of TE movement is different between them. TEs may also be at the origin of important phenotypic differences between both species, and in particular, for the sweet kernel phenotype, a key agronomic character for almond. Here we show that in sweet almond cultivars, highly methylated TE insertions surround a gene of the biosynthesis of amygdalin, whose reduced expression has been correlated with the sweet almond phenotype. Altogether, our results suggest a key role of TEs in the recent history and diversification of almond and its close relative peach.

Comment

[Show More](#)

Organism: [Prunus dulcis \(almond\)](#)

Assembly Name: ALMONDV2

Assembly Title: ALMONDV2 assembly for *Prunus dulcis*

Assembly Level: chromosome

Genome Representation: full

Accession: GCA_902201215

Total Length: 227599157

Ungapped Length: 223688024

N50: 24375383

Spanned Gaps: 3704

Unspanned Gaps: 0

Scaffold Count: 691

Count Contig: 4395

Contig N50: 115182

Contig L50: 511

Contig N75: 58139

Contig N90: 30133

Scaf L50: 4

View: [XML](#)

Download: [XML](#)

[All Seq EMBL](#)

[All Seq FASTA](#)

[WGS Set EMBL](#)

[WGS Set FASTA](#)

Navigation: [Show](#)

Chromosomes: [Show](#)

Assembly Statistics: [Show](#)

WGS Sequence Set: [CABI001](#)

Data Submission at ENA

Data Submission at ENA

- There are three submissions routes
- *'Interactive Submission'*:
 - Use your browser to fill out web forms describing your work
- *'Programmatic Submission'*:
 - Describe your work in XML documents, submit them to us using cURL
- *'Webin-CLI'*:
 - Smart submission interface, made in-house

Data Submission: Interactive

- Register your objects using your browser
- Familiar and largely accessible
- Prepare spreadsheets for bigger submissions

ENA Webin Submissions Portal

Support | Manage Account | Logout (Webin-1)

Register study (project)

Submission Details

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *
22-05-2024

Short descriptive study title *
Testing de novo mutation calling artefacts by re-sequencing single mutation accumulation

Study Name
Arabidopsis mutation accumulation

Will you provide functional genome annotation ?

Detailed study abstract *
To test for the possibility that mutation bias results could in part be artifacts of a pooled-seedling sequencing approach, we re-sequenced entire rosettes of siblings (individual plants) of one mutation accumulation line and asked if the distribution of variation called (i.e., putative somatic mutations around transcription start and termination sites) was similar to the patterns seen with the seedling pools of the 107 individual lines described in the preceding section. Specifically, we grew 10 siblings and extracted DNA from 3-week old whole rosettes. Barcoded PCR-free libraries for

PubMed Citations Registration

Add PubMed Citations +

PubMedId	Title	Remove
9784120	Arabidopsis thaliana: a model plant for genome analysis.	

Data Submission: Programmatic

- Prepare an XML/JSON file describing your submission
- Send this to us via HTTPS
- Correct format for JSON/XML files important for successful submission and validation of data.

- Example cURL command:

```
curl -u username:password \  
-F "SAMPLE=@sample.xml" \  
-F "SUBMISSION=@submission.xml" \  
"https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/drop-box/submit/"
```

```
<SUBMISSION>  
  <ACTIONS>  
    <ACTION>  
      <ADD/>  
    </ACTION>  
  </ACTIONS>  
</SUBMISSION>
```

```
<SAMPLE_SET>  
<SAMPLE alias="MYS176V2" center_name="">  
  <TITLE>human gastric microbiota, mucosal</TITLE>  
  <SAMPLE_NAME>  
    <TAXON_ID>129436</TAXON_ID>  
    <SCIENTIFIC_NAME>stomach metagenome</SCIENTIFIC_NAME>  
    <COMMON_NAME></COMMON_NAME>  
  </SAMPLE_NAME>  
  <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTES>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>collection date</TAG>  
      <VALUE>2010</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>host body site</TAG>  
      <VALUE>Mucosa of stomach</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>human-associated environmental package</TAG>  
      <VALUE>human-associated</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>geographic location (latitude)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>1.81</VALUE>  
      <UNITS>DD</UNITS>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>geographic location (longitude)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>-78.76</VALUE>  
      <UNITS>DD</UNITS>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>geographic location (country and/or sea)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>Colombia</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>geographic location (region and locality)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>Tumaco</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>environment (biome)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>soast</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>project name</TAG>  
      <VALUE>test12V2</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>environment (feature)</TAG>  
      <VALUE>human-associated habitat</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>environmental medium</TAG>  
      <VALUE>gastric fluid</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>broad-scale environmental context</TAG>  
      <VALUE>human gut</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>local environmental context</TAG>  
      <VALUE>human gut</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
    <SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
      <TAG>ENA-CHECKLIST</TAG>  
      <VALUE>ERC000015</VALUE>  
    </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTE>  
  </SAMPLE_ATTRIBUTES>  
</SAMPLE>  
</SAMPLE_SET>
```


ENA - Submission Tools & Data Portals

Interactive Data Submission

Interactive Data Submission: Webin Portal

Welcome to the Webin Submissions Portal

You can use this service for a range of submission activities as well as reports on your submissions. For help with submitting your data, including the use of this interface, please refer to our Help Guides. Please familiarise yourself with the different options available. New users are advised to take a moment to understand the interface.

•Studies tab

- Used for registering studies and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered studies

•Samples tab

- Used to register new samples, requesting taxonomy for novel/unidentified/published species and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered samples

- ENA Metadata Model showing data objects and data structure

•Raw reads/experiments tab

- Used to register runs/experiments and viewing/editing metadata for pre-registered runs/experiments
- Can also be used to track run files validation/processing

Studies (Projects)

Studies Report

- + Register Samples
- + Register Novel Taxonomy
- + Submit XMLs (advanced)

Samples

Samples Report

Raw Reads (Experiments and Runs)

- + Submit XMLs (advanced)
- Runs Report
- Run Files Report
- Run Processing Report
- Unsubmitted Files Report

Data Analyses

Assemblies and annotated sequences must be submitted with **Webin-CLI**. Other analyses can be submitted as XMLs.

- + Generate Annotated Sequence Spreadsheet
- + Submit XMLs (advanced)
- Analyses Report
- Analysis File Report
- Analysis Processing Report

•Analyses tab

- Used to download annotated sequences template spreadsheet and view submitted analyses metadata.
- Can also be used to track analyses files processing.

Interactive Data Submission: Webin Account

- Each submission requires a Webin account.
- Can be created by submitting web form on the Webin Portal page.
- Requires fields such as centre name, country and user credentials.
- Fields such as centre name, contact information can be updated.
- Metagenomics consent box to allow MGnify to access and analyse metagenomic data.

Account Details

Abbreviated center name	Password
Full center name	Confirm Password
Laboratory Name	
Address	
Country	

Contact Information

Add At Least One Contact

No Sensitive Data

I confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable.

Metagenomics Consent

By keeping this box checked you give consent to the EBI MGnify team to analyse those data for which you have requested a pre-publication confidential hold. Note that the data as well as the analysis results will remain confidential until the specified release date of the associated sequencing study. If you are also requesting assembly of your data by MGnify, you also give consent to MGnify to submit these assemblies to your ENA study on your behalf. MGnify will not change any metadata or data you have already submitted but may need to perform updates to submissions performed by their team in exceptional circumstances. This service provides pre-publication state-of-the-art analysis results, along with visualisations, that you may use in subsequent publications. The service is described in <http://europepmc.org/article/MED/31696235> and we kindly request, should you use these analyses in your publications, that you cite this paper.

I give consent and confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable

Save Cancel

Interactive Data Submission: Study

- Study required for each submission at the ENA.
- Groups data objects under one project.
- Authority on release date of data objects linked to a study.
- Add publications and study attributes to study metadata.
- Registered interactively by filling out web form on the Webin Portal.

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Submission Details" with the following sections:

- Submission Details:**
 - Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] * (with a calendar icon)
 - Short descriptive study title
 - Study Name
 - Detailed study abstract (with a text area and a small icon in the bottom right corner)
 - Will you provide functional genome annotation ?
- PubMed Citations Registration:**
 - Add PubMed Citations (+)
- Study Attributes:**
 - Add Study Attributes (+)

At the bottom right, there are two buttons: "Submit" and "Cancel".

Interactive Data Submission: Sample

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O
1	Checklist	ERC000037	ENA Plant Sample Checklist												
2	tax_id	scientific_name	sample_alias	sample_title	sample_description	propagation	collection date	geographic location (latitude)	geographic location (longitude)	plant developmental stage	sample health state	plant developmental stage	ploidy	soil pH	estimated size
3	#units							DD	DD						
4															
5															

- Sample metadata registered using spreadsheets.
- Can register up to 10,000 samples in a single spreadsheet submission.
- Range of sample checklists to choose from including Environmental, Pathogen, Plant and Marine checklists.
- Include required, recommended and mandatory metadata fields.
- Mandatory minimum metadata fields for all checklists include taxonomy information, sample details, collection dates and geographic location.
- #units row includes units for fields where applicable.

Interactive Data Submission: Upload files

- Raw read sequence files need to be uploaded to Webin account before run submission.
- Can use multiple tools to upload files using FTP or Aspera.
- Runs can be submitted using a spreadsheet after upload.

Interactive Data Submission: Run

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	
1	FileType	fastq	Read submission file type										
2	sample	study	instrument_model	library_name	library_source	library_selection	library_strategy	library_layout	forward_file_name	forward_file_md5	reverse_file_name	reverse_file_md5	
3													
4													

- Raw read sequencing data object, final step for submission of raw reads.
- Read files can be submitted using a spreadsheet in the above format.
- Range of read submission checklists to choose from depending on file formats including Fastq, BAM, CRAM, HDF5 and FAST5.
- Read files must be uploaded to the webin account upload area prior to this step
- Successful submission of this spreadsheet returns a run accession with the sequence files metadata and an experiment accession with the library metadata.

Interactive Data Submission

Summary

<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/>

- The ENA provides **scientific record** of sequencing data.
- Established in the early 1980s, extended for **new technologies and applications**.
- Comprehensive record of world's **nucleotide sequencing information** covering raw read data, sequence assembly information and functional annotation.
- Presents large amounts of a diverse range of data in a consistent manner, making use of **data and metadata Models**.
- Metadata model requires minimal mandatory metadata in line with **FAIR data principles**.
- Rich submission, discovery and retrieval **software, tools and services**.
- **Support** through Helpdesk and training.
- **Data submission** routes: Interactive, programmatic and Webin-CLI.
- Interactive Submission using **webin portal** and spreadsheets.
- **Data coordination** including project-specific data hubs and portals.

Handy links

- ENA Browser: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>
- ENA Submission/Retrieval Guide: <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/general-guide.html>
- ENA Helpdesk: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/support>
- Advanced Search: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/advanced-search>
- Webin Portal: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>
- Webin TEST Portal: <https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

Thank you
Any Questions?

Interactive Data Submission Practical

During this exercise, you will implement some of the skills you have just learnt and submit some raw read sequencing data to the ENA.

1. Register a study interactively
2. Register your sample using a spreadsheet
3. Upload raw read data files using FileZilla
4. Submit runs interactively

**Thank you
Any Questions?**

